

**RESPONSIBLE LEADERSHIP AND TRIPLE BOTTOM LINE PERFORMANCE
AMONG FOOD ESTABLISHMENT OWNERS AND MANAGERS AT
BRGY. NEW ISABELA, TACURONG CITY IN THE
CONTEXT OF SDG 8 AND 13**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 21

Issue 8

Pages: 800-808

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2006

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12677039

Manuscript Accepted: 05-27-2024

Responsible Leadership and Triple Bottom Line Performance among Food Establishment Owners and Managers at Brgy. New Isabela, Tacurong City in the Context of SDG 8 and 13

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between responsible leadership and triple bottom line (TBL) performance among food establishment owners and managers in Brgy. New Isabela, Tacurong City, with a focus on Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) and 13 (Climate Action). This study is among the first to explore the role of responsible leadership in TBL performance within the context of local food establishments. The study encompasses 57 respondents, representing a total enumeration of food establishment owners and managers in the area. Employing a quantitative research design with a descriptive-correlational approach, the study utilizes purposive sampling. Adapted and contextualized questionnaires were administered, and data analysis involved Mean, Pearson Moment Correlation, and Multiple Regression Analysis. Findings indicate responsible leadership among food establishment owners and managers in Brgy. New Isabela is characterized by a very high level, notably in stakeholder relations, ethics and values, self-awareness, systems thinking, and change and innovation. TBL performance levels as indicated by the societal, environmental, and economic performance are also assessed as very high. The study reveals a significant relationship between responsible leadership and TBL performance. Additionally, it identifies systems thinking as significantly influencing TBL performance, highlighting its importance in decision-making processes. The implications of the study suggest that responsible leadership plays a crucial role in enhancing both economic and environmental performance within food establishments, aligning with SDGs 8 and 13. By emphasizing the influence of systems thinking on TBL performance, the study advocates for strategic decision-making that benefits not only business operations but also contributes positively to the economy and the environment.

Keywords: *food establishment, responsible leadership, triple bottom line performance, climate action, decent work and economic growth*

Introduction

Organizations are making the fundamental change to survive and prosper by concentrating on lowering costs, eliminating waste, and improving processes. Garcia et al. (2022) research identifies specific leadership practices that are responsible for enhancing innovation performance in small food establishments specializing in merchandise. Observations in Brgy. New Isabela, Tacurong City, indicate that new businesses often fail due to common traits, such as non-strategic placement and lack of marketing strategies. In line with this, businesses are pressured to adopt more sustainable production practices to fulfill their environmental and social obligations (Daddi, 2019).

It is crucial to know that the triple bottom line, explore its historical roots and constraints, and consider various ways it can be integrated into contemporary work environments (Mamatucci & Nair, 2023). Incorporating sustainability into their strategies is crucial for organizations, given the significant role it plays (Correia, 2019). This involves grasping the supplier development strategies encompassing the triple bottom line, which need to be implemented to enhance the sustainability performance of suppliers. Such initiatives are crucial for advancing sustainability throughout the entire supply chain (Pedroso et al., 2021).

Effective leadership plays a vital role in encouraging employees to participate in innovative endeavors that can ultimately have a positive impact on the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) performance (Mantikei, 2020). Sustainable development, as outlined in the triple bottom-line framework, can be described as the concurrent pursuit of objectives in the realms of the economy, the environment, and society (Fathollahi-Fard et al., 2021). Therefore, the pursuit of businesses' goals and objectives while also maintaining good employee relationships contributes to a healthy workplace and successful business, in line with a good TBL performance (Miller, 2020).

To promote innovation and enhance the Triple-Bottom-Line (TBL) performance in the industry, responsible leadership is of paramount importance (Kenton, 2023). In addition, businesses can achieve higher levels of performance in financial, social, and environmental aspects when responsible leadership is in place (Coelho, 2023). Further, the research conducted by Javed et al. (2020) also indicated a significant and positive influence of responsible leadership on all dimensions of TBL performance, which also aligns with the findings highlighted in the study of Decena and Abellanosa (2022), emphasizing the significant impact of responsible leadership on TBL performance.

In context, by carrying out this study, we can better understand the obstacles and chances the industry owners must overcome to pursue a more sustainable and ethical business (Khachatryan, 2023). Thus, the researchers chose to conduct the study utilizing specific indicators such as stakeholder relations, ethics and values, self-awareness, systems thinking, and change and innovation to assess responsible leadership. The evaluation extends beyond leadership to encompass societal performance, environmental performance, and economic performance, collectively contributing to the measurement of Triple Bottom Line (TBL) performance through the lens of

SDGs 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) and 13 (Climate Action). This alignment underscores the research's significance in addressing multifaceted challenges and advancing the global sustainability agenda.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the correlation between responsible leadership and Triple Bottom Line performance among Food Establishments in Brgy. New Isabela, Tacurong City. Specifically, this study had the following objectives:

1. To assess the level of responsible leadership of business owners in terms of:
 - 1.1. stakeholder relation;
 - 1.2. ethics and values;
 - 1.3. self-awareness;
 - 1.4. system thinking; and
 - 1.5. change and innovation?
2. To measure the level of TBL performance of food establishments in terms of:
 - 2.1. societal performance.
 - 2.2. environmental performance; and
 - 2.3. economic performance
3. To determine the relationship between responsible leadership and TBL performance of Food establishments in Brgy. New Isabela, Tacurong City.
4. To determine which domain of responsible leadership influence TBL performance of Food establishments in Brgy. New Isabela, Tacurong City.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational method with a quantitative research methodology. To conduct descriptive research, one must observe and measure without changing any variables. It did recognize traits, patterns, and connections (Siedlecki, 2020). One kind of research design that examined the connections between two or more variables is the correlational study. Non-experimental correlational studies do not involve manipulating or controlling variables (Swart et al., 2019). Given that the general objective of this study was to determine the correlation between responsible leadership and triple bottom line performance among the food establishments in Brgy. New Isabela, Tacurong City, the descriptive-correlational method emerged as the most suitable approach.

Respondents

The selection of respondents followed an accurate methodology wherein purposive sampling was utilized by identifying the participants in consideration with the criteria required for the sample (Nikolopoulou, 2022). To determine the precise population of potential respondents, the researchers conducted a survey in the area Brgy. New Isabela to determine the total number of food establishments within its boundaries.

There were 57 individuals represent the entire population who took part in the study, consenting to their involvement and meeting the outlined criteria: (a) managers who have been employed by the food establishment for at least three (3) months, and (c) and the business should be operational for at least one (1) year. Managers who have recently started their positions and have less than three (3) months of experience, as well as those who work in food establishments that haven't been functioning for at least one (1) year and those outside of the locale of the study were excluded from the study. Respondents had the option to withdraw from participation at any point if they felt uneasy, intimidated, or as though they suffered actual or imagined bodily, psychological, or emotional harm.

Data gathering was conducted from January to February 2024.

Instruments

The questionnaire on responsible leadership and TBL performance were adapted from Decena and Abellanosa (2022). This instrument assessed responsible leadership in the context based on five key factors: stakeholder relations, ethics and values, self-awareness, systems thinking, and change and innovation. While the TBL performance is based on three indicators: environmental, societal, and economic. Respondents' responses will be evaluated using a specific rating scale.

<i>Range of Means</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	This means that responsible leadership and TBL performance are always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This means that responsible leadership and TBL performance are oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that responsible leadership and TBL performance are sometimes observed
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This means that responsible leadership and TBL performance are rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means that responsible leadership and TBL performance are not observed

Procedure

To collect the necessary data for this study, several procedures were undertaken. Initially, permission to conduct the research was sought from the school authorities. Subsequently, the questionnaire undergone validation by professional validators where in the questionnaire obtained a total average of 4.5 from the validators, indicating that the questionnaire's content was "Excellent".

Following the validation, the researcher conducted a pilot test with a group of food establishment owners and managers in Brgy. New Isabela. To assess the questionnaire's reliability, the Cronbach alpha coefficient was also employed where the independent variable, responsible leadership, yielded a rating of 0.705, indicating "acceptable". On the other hand, the dependent variable, TBL performance, had the rating of 0.843, indicating that the content was "good".

After the validity and reliability were established, full blast collection of data was conducted by accumulating the participant's responses on the survey questionnaire. Lastly, data analysis and interpretation were conducted, where the results were assessed and explained.

Data Analysis

The data that were gathered from the questionnaires were analyzed and tailed using the following statistical tools:

Mean. It was used to determine the level of responsible leadership and triple bottom line performance.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation. This was used to determine the relationship between responsible leadership and triple bottom line performance.

Multiple Regression. This was used to know which domain of responsible leadership influence triple bottom line performance.

Ethical Considerations

Throughout the study, the researcher maintained ethical principles and standards by diligently adhering to the study protocol, assessments, and standardized criteria. Notably, these guidelines were strictly followed regarding population management and data handling, as outlined below:

Voluntary Participation: Respondents in this study were given the choice to participate or not, at their discretion. Potential respondents were approached and provided with an explanation procedure, including detailed information on their rights to withdraw or refuse the study.

Privacy and Confidentiality: Respondents were not compelled to disclose personal information if they chose not to. Researchers respected respondents' privacy and ensured no harm or coercion was inflicted upon them.

Informed Consent Process: Respondents were adequately informed about the study's purpose, risks, benefits, and their rights. Sufficient time was provided for them to read and understand the materials, ask questions, and voice concerns.

Plagiarism: Proper recognition and citation of all sources were ensured to avoid plagiarism or irregularity. Additionally, Turnitin plagiarism detector was utilized.

Fabrication: The study was based on reliable investigations, ensuring that the researcher did not fabricate data or conclusions but accurately represented existing literature.

Falsification: Data were not embellished or misrepresented to fit preconceived notions or false claims.

Conflict of Interest (COI): Data collection techniques that could result in a conflict of interest were avoided. The study focused solely on the validity of analytical results and the well-being of respondents, without being influenced by any side interests.

Deceit: Respondents were assured that providing information would not harm them, and the researcher did not deceive or dishonestly manipulate them.

Permission from Organization/Location: Written authorization was obtained from proper authorities.

Authorship: Contributions of individuals were accurately represented, with the research adviser considered a co-author. Co-authors must secure consent from others before using the study.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the evaluation of responsible leadership among food establishment owners and managers in New Isabela, Tacurong City. The total mean score is 4.33, which is very high. This means that their responsible leadership is always observed. Self-awareness had the highest mean score of 4.39, with a description of "always observed," whereas systems thinking had the lowest mean score of 4.27 but still got the same interpretation.

Table 1. *Level of Responsible Leadership*

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Level
Stakeholder Relation	4.36	Very High
Ethics and Values	4.31	Very High
Self-Awareness	4.39	Very High
Systems thinking	4.27	Very High
Change and Innovation	4.34	Very High
Overall	4.33	Very High

Level of Triple Bottom Line of Food Establishments Owner/Manager

Table 2 presents the triple bottom line performance among food establishment owners and managers in New Isabela, Tacurong City. The total mean score is 4.27, indicating a very high level of performance, suggesting that it is always achieved across all evaluated aspects. Whereas the societal performance garnered the highest mean score of 4.35, indicating that it is always achieved. On the other hand, environmental performance got the lowest mean score of 4.19, suggesting that it is only achieved oftentimes.

Table 2. *Level of Triple Bottom Line Performance*

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Level
Societal Performance	4.35	Very High
Environmental Performance	4.19	High
Economic Performance	4.27	Very High
Overall	4.27	Very High

Significant Relationship Between Responsible Leadership and Triple Bottom Line Performance among Food Establishment Owners/Managers

The findings from Table 3 provide compelling evidence of a significant relationship between Responsible Leadership and Triple Bottom Line (TBL) Performance among Food Establishment Owners in Brgy. New Isabela, Tacurong City. This statistical analysis, with a p-value of less than 0.011 and a correlation coefficient (r-value) of 0.333*, indicates a low positive correlation between these two variables. The results suggest that Responsible Leadership, even though it is low, still correlates with TBL Performance among food establishment owners/managers in the area.

Table 3. *Significant Relationship Between Responsible Leadership and Triple Bottom Line Performance among Food Establishment Owners in Brgy. New Isabela, Tacurong City*

Category	p-value	r-value	Significant
Responsible Leadership vs Triple Bottom Line Performance	P<0.011	0.333*	Low Positive Correlation

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Multiple Regression Analysis of the Responsible Leadership Domains towards Triple Bottom Line Performance

Table 4 presents the findings from the computed multiple regression analysis regarding how responsible leadership factors impact triple bottom line performance. Beyond the significance threshold of 0.05, the p-values for ethics and values, stakeholder relations, change and innovation, and self-awareness were 0.838, 0.739, 0.625, and 0.442, respectively. However, the p-value for systems thinking is .002, which falls below the significance threshold of 0.05. Since the estimated p-value for systems thinking is less than the significance threshold of 0.05, null hypothesis number 2, which posits that there is no domain of responsible leadership that influences triple bottom line performance, is rejected. This rejection implies that the influence of most variables on triple bottom line performance is minimal, with only one indicator significantly affecting it.

Table 4. *Multiple Regression Analysis of the Responsible Leadership Domains towards Triple Bottom Line Performance*

	Responsible Leadership	
Triple Bottom Line Performance		p-value
Stakeholder Relation	.739	Not Significant
Ethics and Values	.838	Not Significant
Self-Awareness	.442	Not Significant
Systems Thinking	.002	Significant
Change and Innovation	.625	Not Significant

Level of Responsible Leadership of Food Establishments Owner/Manager

The findings from Table 1 underscore the consistent adherence of food establishment owners and managers to responsible leadership practices. This observation aligns with the scholarly works of Muff (2020), which emphasize the necessity for leaders to possess broader

collaboration competencies to effectively engage with stakeholders. These competencies are integral components of the established literature on responsible leadership (RL) competencies. Similarly, Voegtlin et al. (2020) corroborates this assertion in their systematic review, highlighting the significant attention given to ethics and values in leadership and their impact on firm performance. Furthermore, Brewer and Deynew (2022) contribute to this discourse by delineating effective pedagogical techniques for cultivating heightened self-awareness, a fundamental aspect of responsible management and leadership. Moreover, Pyster (2021) insights underscore the imperative of continuous innovation in today's competitive landscape, emphasizing its pivotal role in organizational success.

The research conducted by Cai et al. (2022) adds another dimension by revealing a direct relationship between stakeholder engagement and leadership potential, corroborating the outcomes observed in this study. The increasing academic and corporate interest in ethical leadership and corporate social responsibility, as highlighted by Saha et al. (2020), further supports the significance of responsible leadership practices. This sentiment is echoed in Sinurat (2021) study, which recognizes the pivotal role of self-awareness in enhancing managerial competence. Additionally, Cave (2022) asserts the value of systems thinking as a framework for comprehending the complexities of organizational operations. Finally, Alvarez (2024) emphasis on innovation as a catalyst for change and corporate success underscores the importance of adaptability and proactive management strategies.

Level of Triple Bottom Line Performance of Food Establishments Owner/Manager

The results from table 2 underscore that food establishments achieved a very high triple bottom line performance. This indicates that the food establishments value the establishment of their moral standing and ensure the safety of their products and consumers. This aligns with the study of Miller (2023) stating that businesses should make a commitment to assess their social and environmental impact, alongside their financial performance. In addition, the study of Alvarez (2024) also revealed that food services' primary concerns turned out to be marketing methods related to their goods and services, costs, distribution locations, and sales promotion. Also, businesses have ensured the safety of their products and consumers and reduced their carbon footprint. Furthermore, findings from Perramon et al. (2019) study indicate that taking proactive measures toward environmental concerns can yield numerous advantages for restaurants, enhancing their competitiveness and overall performance. As Laverty and Littel (2020) stated, businesses also strived for a more sustainable way of gaining profit and reducing the total operation cost. Their goal is also satisfying consumers' demands and implement a "green" strategy. The result also supported by the study of Barbosa et al. (2022) that suggested that all three measurements of supportability (natural, social, and financial) have been emphatically influenced by an increment in natural collaboration, with a lower impact watched on the financial measurement. Lastly, Camanzi et al. (2019) study findings also highlight the significance of informal contractual agreements within a local production system characterized by strong social bonds. These arrangements lead to enhanced product quality and improved economic outcomes.

Significant Relationship Between Responsible Leadership and Triple Bottom Line Performance among Food Establishment Owners/Managers

These findings underscore the imperative for businesses, particularly within the restaurant industry of Brgy. New Isabela, Tacurong City, to adopt Responsible Leadership practices. Responsible leadership, as it involves a multifaceted approach that includes considerations for social impact, pragmatic innovation, and the integration of diversity (Cave, 2022). It is not merely about profitability, but also about creating value for all stakeholders, including employees, customers, and the community (Camilleri, 2017). This observation also aligns with the body of research of Haque et al. (2019) that emphasizes the positive impact of Responsible Leadership on business outcomes and sustainability. It highlights the critical role that leaders play in fostering a business environment that not only prioritizes financial success but also considers social and environmental responsibility in a study of Voegtlin et al. (2020). This holistic approach to leadership is further supported by Camilleri (2017) who emphasizes the crucial role of responsibility in leadership, highlighting how it contributes to organizational success and long-term sustainability.

Multiple Regression Analysis of the Responsible Leadership Domains towards Triple Bottom Line Performance

As emphasized in Boylston (2019), the systems thinking approach establishes a direct connection between service system design and improved environmental and social benefits, while also indirectly fostering economic benefits, as supported by the findings presented in Table 4. Additionally, Mooney (2020) mentioned that systems thinking has been evolving and applied across various disciplines including management, economics, and engineering over recent decades. Furthermore, according to Cave (2022), systems thinking assists organizations in understanding the growing complexities within their operations and within the broader global context.

Conclusions

The level of responsible leadership is very high, which means that it is always observed by the owner/manager of food establishment in the Brgy. New Isabela, Tacurong City. It also showed that all indicators of the responsible leaders are very high, indicating that all of it was always observed by the respondents.

The level of TBL performance is very high, indicating that it is always achieved by the owner/manager of food establishment in the Brgy. New Isabela, Tacurong City wherein societal and economic performance showed to be always achieved. However, environmental performance turned out to be only oftentimes achieved by the respondents.

There is a low positive correlation between responsible leadership and TBL performance of food establishment owners/manager at Brgy. New Isabela, Tacurong City.

Only systems thinking domain of responsible leadership significantly influence TBL performance and all other indicators affected it only minimally.

Since the level of responsibility is very high, the research recommends owners and managers to continuously maintain and improve their stakeholder relations, self-awareness, ethics, and innovation as they operate their businesses. However, they need to enhance their systems thinking abilities by comprehensively understanding the different issues they encountered.

The level of TBL performance is also very high, however, the researchers still recommend owners and managers to focus more on reducing carbon footprints, such as replacing energy and water-consuming appliances, to sustainably enhance their environmental performance while keeping on track on their societal and economic performance.

There is a low positive correlation between responsible leadership and TBL performance, the researcher recommends that they should strategize on meeting the sustainability targets while minimizing costs, particularly through environmental strategies aligned with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Only systems thinking domain of responsible leadership significantly influence TBL performance, the researchers recommend prioritizing the strengthening in areas such as stakeholder relations, ethics, and values. This involves increased engagement across diverse teams and reinforcing ethical behavior among employees while also enhancing the self-awareness of the owners and managers by understanding their own strengths, weaknesses, and their possible impact to other and fostering the change and innovation within their business by encouraging risk-taking and experimentation.

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